

Neural correlates and functional connectivity of lexical tone processing in reading

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Abstract

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Lexical tone processing in speech is mediated by bilateral superior temporal and inferior prefrontal regions, but little is known concerning the neural circuitries of lexical tone phonology in reading. Using fMRI, we examined the neural systems for lexical tone in visual Chinese word recognition. We found that the extraction of lexical tone phonology in print was subserved by bilateral fronto-parietal regions. Seed-to-voxel analyses showed that functionally connected cortical regions involved right inferior frontal gyrus and SMA, right middle frontal gyrus and right inferior parietal lobule, and SMA and bilateral cingulate gyri. Our results indicate that in Chinese tone reading, a bilateral network of frontal, parietal, motor, and cingulate regions is engaged, without involvement of temporal regions crucial for tone identification in auditory domain. Although neural couplings for lexical tone processing are different in speech and reading to some degree, the motor cortex seems to be a key component independent of modality.

1. Introduction

Lexical tone is characterized by pitch variations at the syllable level, and it is used to convey grammatical or word meanings in more than half of the world's languages (Maddieson, 2013; Yip, 2002). Given the importance of lexical tone processing in language comprehension, the functional anatomy of lexical tone processing in speech has been intensively investigated over a century. In the auditory domain, a large number of neuroimaging studies have revealed that lexical tone processing in speech is subserved by a bi-lateralized cortical network involving superior temporal regions, inferior prefrontal regions and the insula (Chang, Lee, Tzeng, & Kuo, 2014; Gandour et al., 2000; Hsieh, Gandour, Wong, & Hutchins, 2001; Klein, Zatorre, Milner, & Zhao, 2001; Kwok et al., 2016, 2017; Liang & Du, 2018; Liu, Peng, et al., 2006; Luo et al., 2006; Nan & Friederici, 2013; Ren, Yang, & Li, 2009; Schremm et al., 2018; Wong, Parsons, Martinez, & Diehl, 2004; Xi, Zhang, Shu, Zhang, & Li, 2010; Yu, Wang, Li, & Li, 2014). Several studies have also illustrated left-lateralized connectivity network for lexical tone processing in speech (Ge et al., 2015; Xu, Wang, Chen, Fox, & Tan, 2015; Yang, Gates, Molenaar, & Li, 2015). In the visual domain, phonology has a role in activating word meanings in skilled silent reading (Coltheart, 2000; DeMarco, Wilson, Rising, Rapcsak, & Beeson, 2017; Jared, Levy, & Rayner, 1999; Ryherd et al., 2018; Tan & Perfetti,

1999), and thus, it is reasonable to postulate the contribution of lexical tone phonology to visual word recognition. Yet, in tonal languages such as Mandarin, there is no indication of tone when reading a Chinese character, and our understanding of how the human brain processes lexical tone information embedded in the Chinese characters to facilitate reading remains superficial.

Previous behavioral and electrophysiological studies have addressed the unique contribution of lexical tone to successful character recognition and reading acquisition (Li, Lin, Wang, & Jiang, 2013; Nixon, Chen, & Schiller, 2015; Pollatsek, Tan, & Rayner, 2000; Verdonschot, Lai, Chen, Tamaoka, & Schiller, 2015; Wang, Li, & Lin, 2015). For instance, proficient knowledge in lexical tone phonology of characters is associated with better reading performance in Chinese children (Shu, Peng, & McBride-Chang, 2008; Tong, Tong, & McBride-Chang, 2015). Li, Wang, and Yang (2014) have demonstrated the contribution of tonal information in Chinese reading with a Stroop paradigm. They modified the color naming task (i.e. the Stroop task) from Spinks, Liu, Perfetti, and Tan (2000) by adding an extra stimulus type, which were non-homophones sharing only the same tone with the color characters (e.g., 红 /hong2/, 'red' vs. 瓶 /ping2/, 'bottle'). The authors observed significant Stroop facilitation in these same-tone trials and thus, proposed that both segmental and tonal information are activated automatically in the process of visual word recognition. In a

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visual mismatch negativity (MMN) study, Wang, Liu, Wu, and Wang (2013) have observed automatic extraction of lexical tone information embedded in Chinese characters. Participants were presented standard stimuli that had an identical syllable with the same tone (e.g., 议 /yi4/), or deviants that had the same syllable differed in tones (e.g. 依/yi1/ 移/yi2/ 以/yi3/). Results showed that the deviant stimuli evoked significant MMN responses, suggesting the presence of lexical tone processing in reading at an early pre-attentive stage. These findings suggest that segmental and lexical tone phonology were both crucial in successful reading.

Our previous work used fMRI to demonstrate the neural signatures of lexical tone processing in Chinese reading (Kwok et al., 2015). Participants were required to judge whether the monosyllabic character presented on each trial carried the high-falling tone, where the baseline condition was an arrow direction judgment asking participants to indicate whether the arrow pointed upward or downward. Our results showed that, lexical tone processing in reading Chinese characters activated brain regions in frontal lobes, parietal lobes, temporal lobes and visual systems bilaterally, but the overall activations were stronger in the left hemisphere. Nevertheless, the baseline condition used in that study was not language-related and was not able to fractionate cortical activations evoked by lexical tone processing from other linguistic processes, such as orthographic or semantic processing. It is thus less convincing to argue that those findings were purely associated with lexical tone processing.

The current study aimed to elucidate the brain basis of lexical tone processing in Chinese reading. A lexical tone discrimination task was devised where participants were asked to distinguish whether or not the two Chinese characters in a disyllabic word carried the same lexical tone. In the control task, participants judged whether or not the two synchronously exposed Chinese characters had the same physical size. We contrasted the cortical activities during lexical tone discrimination and font size judgment. Expanding our knowledge in lexical tone reading, we also conducted a functional connectivity analysis based on the imaging results of the lexical tone discrimination task, to look into cortical connections involved in lexical tone reading.

2. Method

2.1. Participants

Seventeen Beijing college students participated in this functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) study (8 males and 9 females; average age = 21.1 years, SD = 0.49 years). All participants were healthy, native speakers of Mandarin and were strongly right-handed. They had normal or corrected-to-normal vision. This study was approved by the Institutional Review Board of Beijing MRI Center for Brain Research, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

2.2. Design and materials

Forty-eight disyllabic words were randomly selected from the Modern Chinese Frequency Dictionary (Wang, 1986) with high frequency of occurrences. Meaningful, disyllabic words were presented and participants were required to make same-different tone judgments of the two characters in a word on each trial. In half of the trials, tone of the two characters was identical (e.g. 参加 /can1/ /jia1/, participate in). In the rest of the trials, tones of the two syllables were different (e.g. 历史 /li4/ /shi3/, history). The baseline task was character font size judgment, in which participants were asked to judge whether the displayed characters had the same physical size. Participants responded by making button presses by left or right index finger. For the same-tone trials, Tone 3 words were excluded to avoid any tone confusion induced by the tone sandhi effect. All four tones were included in different-tone trials.

2.3. Experimental procedures

The lexical tone discrimination task consisted of 4 experimental blocks of the Chinese lexical tone discrimination task altered by 4 blocks of character font size judgment baseline. The task started with a 6-s fixation crosshair, followed by a 2-s task instruction before the task began. Disyllabic words were presented for 1000 ms on each trial, followed by a blank interval of 1500 ms for participants to respond. Character font size judgment baseline required participants to judge whether the physical sizes of the character pairs displayed were identical, and were required to make button presses accordingly. Task instruction was presented for 2 s before each block. Prior to scan, all participants were given sufficient practice to familiarize with task procedures, and stimulus words used in the practice section did not reoccur during the scan.

2.4. MRI acquisition

Functional images were acquired on a 3T Siemens scanner at Beijing 306 hospital using a T2*-weighted, gradient-echo echo planar imaging (EPI) sequence (TE = 30 ms, TR = 2000 ms, flip angle = 90°, field of view = 21 cm, slice thickness = 4 mm, and image matrix = 64 × 64). Thirty axial slices were acquired with full brain coverage. Three-dimensional, high-resolution anatomical scans (1 × 1 × 1 mm) were also acquired for each subject. Visual stimuli were presented through a projector onto a translucent screen and participants viewed the screen through a mirror attached to the head coil.

2.5. fMRI data analysis

The fMRI data analysis was performed using the Statistical Parametric Mapping software package (SPM8; <http://www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm>). After data conversion, participants' data were preprocessed in batch model one by one. The first three volumes of each participant's scan were discarded, and the remaining functional images were corrected for slice-timing and head motion effects. Functional images were then co-registered with the individual high-resolution T1 anatomical images and spatially normalized to the Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) stereotaxic template, resampled into 2 × 2 × 2 mm cubic voxels. The normalized images were then spatially smoothed with a full-width half maximum (FWHM) isotropic Gaussian kernel of 8 mm. Individual activation maps were generated by using the general linear model (GLM), time series were convolved with the canonical hemodynamic response function, high-pass filtered at 128 s to remove low-frequency components and included the six head motion parameters as nuisance regressors. The random-effects model was used to obtain contrast images in second-level group analysis. Whole brain activation of lexical tone phonology in reading was examined by a one sample t-test, which was the group contrasts of brain activations in the lexical tone discrimination task (i.e., lexical tone > font size). All statistical maps were thresholded at $P < 0.05$ false discovery rate (FDR-) corrected for multiple comparisons. Brain regions were estimated from Talairach and Tournoux, after adjustments for differences between MNI and Talairach coordinates (Talairach & Tournoux, 1988).

2.6. Condition-dependent functional connectivity analysis

2.6.1. Definition of seeds

The functional connectivity analysis computed the seeded correlations between the signal from a seed region and that at other brain voxels during task conditions. The aim of our functional connectivity analysis was to examine the network of cortical regions engaging lexical tone processing in reading. A total of 8 spherical seeds (regions of interests, ROIs) were defined as the local maxima based on the brain activations found in lexical tone processing in reading, to ensure that the selected seed regions were relevant to lexical tone processing. All

selected regions were also previously identified in lexical tone processing in reading (Kwok et al., 2015). Table 2 showed the coordinates of all seed ROIs, spherical seeds were created with 6-mm radius in Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) coordinates, including the supplementary motor area (SMA; BA6, x = 6, y = 22, z = 48), right pre-central gyrus (BA6, x = 42, y = 4, z = 42), right IFG (BA45, x = 32, y = 26, z = 6; BA45/46, x = 46, y = 44, z = 6), right middle frontal gyrus (BA10/46, x = 40, y = 44, z = 3), right insula (x = 28, y = 26, z = 6), left insula (x = -36, y = 20, z = 10), and right cingulate gyrus (BA 32, x = 16, y = 20, z = 36).

2.6.2. Preprocessing and correlation analysis

A seed-to-voxel correlation analysis was performed by the functional connectivity (CONN) toolbox version 16b and SPM8. The functional images were preprocessed following the pipeline within the toolbox. The CompCor strategy was implemented, motion parameters and their derivatives, white matter, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) were added as regressors to remove variance relevant to head motion, global signal, white matter and CSF. Data were band-pass filtered (0.008 < f < inf Hz) based on an active task (i.e. lexical tone > font size). Correlation coefficients between the time-courses of seeds and the activated voxels in the brain were obtained and z-transformed for General Linear Model analyses. Images from the first-level results provided the seed-to-voxel connectivity maps for each selected ROI for each subject for each task condition (i.e., lexical tone discrimination and font size judgment). Individual functional connectivity maps were performed with both parametric and non-parametric approaches for group difference analysis using one-sample t test. To avoid false positive results (Eklund, Nichols, & Knutsson, 2016), we chose to report non-parametric statistics thresholded at the P < 0.001 uncorrected at voxel level, P < 0.05 FWE-corrected at cluster-mass level.

3. Results

3.1. Behavioral performance

Participants were highly accurate in both conditions during the task. After excluding incorrect trials (6.9%), mean accuracy was 89%(SD = 7.6) in lexical tone reading of disyllabic words, and the average reaction time was 1192 ms (SD = 235). Mean accuracy was 98%(SD = 2) in font size judgment of disyllabic words, and the average reaction time was 622 ms (SD = 69).

3.2. Imaging results

Significant areas of activation for lexical tone vs. font size judgment averaged across 17 participants are shown in Fig. 1 and Table 1. Peak activations were observed in frontal regions bilaterally in Mandarin natives, but was much stronger in the left hemisphere, encompassing

Table 1
Coordinates of activation peaks for the contrast of Chinese tone reading minus font-size judgment.

Regions activated	BA	Z score	x	y	z
Frontal					
L precentral gyrus	6	4.79	-38	-1	33
R precentral gyrus	44	3.93	38	14	9
Supplementary motor area	6	4.71	4	12	46
	6	4.13	-6	12	44
	31	4.55	-10	-31	18
Cingulate gyrus	32	4.13	-10	18	34
	31	5.03	17	-40	21
	32	3.99	10	18	34
	9	5.3	-46	16	24
L middle frontal gyrus	6	3.1	33	3	53
R middle frontal gyrus	44	4.26	-38	3	30
L inferior frontal gyrus	45	4.55	-27	24	8
	47	4.3	29	22	-1
R inferior frontal gyrus	-	4.47	-32	16	9
L insula	-	4.46	26	20	3
R insula	-	4.61	24	22	6
Parietal					
L inferior parietal lobule	40	3.62	-29	-54	34
Other areas					
L caudate R	-	4.57	-22	-44	6
caudate R	-	4.41	22	-44	8
thalamus R	-	4.83	-12	-9	3
putamen L	-	4.28	-1	-44	-22
cerebellum	-	3.09	-1	-40	-45
R cerebellum	-	5.03	19	-66	-42
	-	4.23	22	-58	-47

Stereotaxic coordinates (mm) are derived from the human brain atlas of Talairach and Tournoux (1998) and refer to the peak Z scores for each region (P < 0.05, FDR-corrected) at voxel level for multiple comparisons.

Table 2
Mean coordinates of all selected seed ROIs in MNI space in computing functional connectivity for the tone reading experiment.

Anatomical region	BA	x	y	z
Supplementary motor area	6	6	22	48
R precentral gyrus	6	42	4	42
R inferior frontal gyrus R	44/45	32	26	6
middle frontal gyrus	10/46	40	44	3
R inferior frontal gyrus	46	46	44	6
Cingulate gyrus	32	16	20	36
R insula	-	28	26	6
L insula	-	-36	20	10

precentral gyrus (BAs 6, 44), SMA (BA6), inferior frontal gyrus (BAs 44, 45), middle frontal gyrus (BAs 6, 9), insula, cingulate gyrus (BAs 31, 32), and cerebellum. Activation was also found in the left inferior

Fig. 1. Lateral view and axial sections of the brain regions with significant activity of lexical tone perception in Chinese reading at P < 0.05 FDR-corrected for multiple comparisons. The functional maps (in color) are overlaid on the corresponding T1 images (in gray scale). Planes are axial sections, labeled with the height (mm) relative to the bicommissural line. L = the left hemisphere; R = the right hemisphere.

Fig. 2. Significant functional connectivity observed in the contrast of tone reading relative to font size judgment. With non-parametric approach, height threshold at $p < 0.001$ uncorrected, cluster mass at $p < 0.05$ FWE-corrected level. (a) The right inferior frontal seed is connected to the right superior frontal/SMA; (b) the right middle frontal seed is connected to the right inferior parietal lobule; (c) the SMA seed is connected with the cingulate gyrus; (d) lateral view of all seeds and target regions. L = left hemisphere; R = right hemisphere.

parietal lobule (BA40). Subcortical activations were observed in caudate, thalamus, putamen and caudate.

3.3. Functional connectivity for lexical tone reading

We found several significant functional connections between seeds and other voxels within the whole brain, as shown in Fig. 2 and Table 3 ($P < 0.001$ uncorrected at voxel level, $P < 0.05$ FWE-corrected at cluster-mass level). One seed was defined in the right middle frontal gyrus (RMFG; BA10/46) and the other was in the right inferior frontal gyrus (RIFG; BA45/46), they were spatially different and were strongly activated in processing lexical tone information of written characters. The RMFG seed was positively correlated to the right supramarginal gyrus and the right inferior parietal lobule (BA40; cluster size = 306; $r = 0.15$, $p = 0.008$), and the RIFG seed was positively correlated to the right superior frontal gyrus/ SMA (BA6; cluster size = 177; $r = 0.18$, $p = 0.05$). While another strongly activated seed region, the SMA, was significantly connected to the left and right cingulate gyri respectively

Table 3
Task dependent functional connectivity between seed regions and other voxels within the whole brain.

Seed ROI	Target region	BA	x	y	z	Z score	Cluster size
Positive correlations Supplementary motor area	Cingulate gyrus	24	-4	10	37	4.74	304
		24/32	6	6	39	4.54	
		32	1	16	36	4.26	
R inferior frontal gyrus	Supplementary motor area	6	13	-3	59	4.88	177
	Supplementary motor area	6	19	-1	54	4.61	
	R paracentral lobule	24	15	-9	43	3.71	
R middle frontal gyrus	R inferior parietal lobule	40	57	-27	27	4.06	306
		40	47	-29	39	3.77	
	R inferior parietal lobule/supramarginal gyrus	40	61	-34	26	3.98	

Stereotaxic coordinates (mm) are derived from the human brain atlas of Talairach and Tournoux (1998) and refer to the peak Z scores for each region ($p < 0.001$ at voxel level, $p < 0.05$ FWE-corrected at cluster-mass level) in non-parametric approach.

(BA24, 32; cluster size = 304; $r = 0.2$, $p = 0.018$). No significant connections were observed for the rest of the seed regions.

4. Discussion

The present study examined the brain mechanisms supporting lexical tone phonology in visual Chinese word recognition. We found that lexical tone phonology was mediated by the fronto-parietal network, composed by bilateral frontal regions and the left inferior parietal lobe. Cortical activations in the bilateral frontal areas included the SMA, precentral gyri, inferior and middle frontal gyri, insular and cingulate gyri.

Bilateral inferior frontal gyri, insular, cingulate gyri and the precentral gyri were consistently active in lexical tone processing in speech (Chang et al., 2014; Gandour et al., 2000; Klein et al., 2001; Kwok et al., 2016, 2017; Liang & Du, 2018; Nan & Friederici, 2013; Wong et al., 2004, 2008). When participants were required to make lexical tone judgments in silent reading, they had to generate or retrieve auditory

information in the absence of sound perception. Peak activation in the SMA also reflected participants' effort in auditory imagery (Lima, Krishnan, & Scott, 2016; Tian, Zarate, & Poeppel, 2016), a process in retrieving tonal information of the characters without the presence of auditory stimuli. Activation in the left inferior parietal lobule was frequently found in language tasks, such as orthography-to-phonology transformation (Bitan et al., 2007; Booth et al., 2006; Cao et al., 2009), phonological processing of auditory and visual inputs (Booth et al., 2006; Deschamps, Baum, & Gracco, 2014; Liu et al., 2009; Seghier et al., 2004; Sliwinska, Khadijkar, Campbell-Ratcliffe, Quevenco, & Devlin, 2012; Tan et al., 2003, Tan, Laird, Li, & Fox, 2005), and lexical tone judgment (Gandour et al., 2003; Kwok et al., 2015; Li et al., 2003). Some have considered the inferior parietal region as part of the phonological loop (Cohen et al., 1997; Paulesu, Frith, & Frackowiak, 1993). We assume the parietal region is crucial in phonological processing of tonal information. Previous connectivity studies concerning lexical tone perception have focused on the cortical connections among left hemispheric regions (Ge et al., 2015; Xu et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2015). Based on our findings, the right frontal regions were also strongly activated in lexical tone reading. Thus, we aimed to explore the connectivity networks of lexical tone processing among right hemispheric regions.

With the SMA as seed region, positive correlations were found in the cingulate gyri (BA24, 32) bilaterally. Both the SMA and cingulate gyrus were consistently implicated in auditory imagery (Hubbard, 2010; Lima et al., 2016; Meyer, Elmer, Baumann, & Jancke, 2007) and auditory lexical tone processing (Gandour et al., 1998, 2000; Klein et al., 2001; Chang et al., 2014). Previous studies have also revealed the importance of the cingulate gyrus in attentional control (Milham et al., 2001; Milham, Banich, Claus, & Cohen, 2003) and phonological processing in Chinese reading (Wu, Ho, & Chen, 2012). The right inferior frontal gyrus (BA45/46) seed revealed positive correlations in the right SMA/superior frontal gyrus (BA6). The superior frontal gyrus and SMA were relevant to phonological working memory processes (Heim, Opitz, Müller, & Friederici, 2003), phonological segmentation and articulatory control (Booth, Wood, Lu, Houk, & Bitan, 2007; Poldrack et al., 1999), phonological and semantic processing of Chinese characters (Li, Jin, & Tan, 2004; Tan, Liu, et al., 2001; Wu et al., 2012). These functional connections between the motor cortex and the frontal regions also illustrated the successful formation of long-term motor memories of Chinese characters in skilled adult readers (Tan, Spinks, Eden, Perfetti, & Siok, 2005). Moreover, reading skills are built on adequate spoken language development, and phonological processes are critical to successful reading acquisition (Brown, 1970; Liberman & Liberman, 1990). Since tone perception in speech involves a functional link between motor and perceptual representations of speech sounds (Barnaud, Bessièrè, Diard, & Schwartz, 2018; d'Ausilio et al., 2009; Liebenthal & Möttönen, 2017; Nuttall, Kennedy-Higgins, Devlin, & Adank, 2018; Pulvermüller & Fadiga, 2010; Si, Zhou, & Hong, 2017; Wan, Hancock, Moon, & Gillam, 2018), hypothetically, the motor cortex may also be a key component of lexical tone and phonological processing in reading.

The right middle frontal gyrus (BA10/46) was functionally connected with the right inferior parietal lobule and right supramarginal gyrus (BA40). Some recent studies have revealed the role of right middle frontal gyrus in orthographic processing (Liu, Hue, et al., 2006) and semantic processing in Chinese reading (Wu et al., 2012). While the inferior parietal system is frequently involved in Chinese reading, it is activated during phonological processing of Chinese characters (Tan et al., 2000, 2003), orthography-to-phonology mapping in Chinese reading (Booth et al., 2006; Cao et al., 2009), acting as a temporary storage of phonological information in working memory (Booth et al., 2006; Ravizza, Delgado, Chein, Becker, & Fiez, 2004; Tan, Spinks, et al., 2005).

More importantly, the superior temporal gyrus, a prominent region in speech and non-speech pitch processing (Bauernfeind, Wriessnegger, Haumann, & Lenarz, 2018; Binder et al., 2000; Ge et al., 2015; Kwok et al., 2017; Nan & Friederici, 2013; Price, Thierry, & Griffiths, 2005; Zatorre, Belin, & Penhune, 2002), was not involved in lexical tone processing in reading. We also did not observe any connections between the STG and other voxels within the brain in our lexical tone dis-crimination task. Thus, our findings are consistent with Kwok et al. (2015) that the role of superior temporal gyrus in lexical tone perception depends on the input modality. A potential limitation of the current study is that some process differences might be involved in lexical tone judgment vs. font size judgments of characters. Since the control task only required the participants to judge the physical size of characters, other higher level process differences between these two conditions could occur besides lexical tone perception. Two or more control tasks of different levels should be included to deal with these process differences in future lexical tone reading studies.

Together, this study has shown a bi-lateralized cortical network for processing lexical tone phonology in reading. The involvement of the superior temporal gyrus is modality-specific. Functionally connected cortical regions in lexical tone reading involved the right inferior frontal gyrus and SMA, the right middle frontal gyrus and right inferior parietal lobule/supramarginal gyrus, and SMA and bilateral cingulate gyri.

5. Statement of significance

This study is the first to investigate functional connectivity of lexical tone reading, and it suggests that neural systems for lexical tone processing in speech and reading are different to some degree. Results also implicate the potential contribution of the motor cortex to lexical tone and phonological processing in reading, and thus, expand our knowledge of the motor theory of auditory tone perception to the visual modality.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandl.2019.104662>.

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